

Stereochemistry of addition of organometallic reagents to 2-acyloxanes and 2-acylthianes[†]

Maria Teresa Alvarez-Wright, Hikmet Satici, Ernest L. Eliel* and Peter S. White

W. R. Kenan, Jr. Laboratories, Department of Chemistry, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC 27599-3290, U.S.A.

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The stereochemistry of addition of a number of organometallic reagents, including methylolithium, methylolithium-YbCl₃, 1-pentynyllithium, and 1-pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ to 2-acyloxanes, 2-benzoylthianes, several substituted 1,3-oxathianes and 2-methoxyacetylthiane has been studied. For the ring systems containing oxygen atoms, almost all of the additions proceed in accordance with Cram's chelate rule, on the assumption that the chelation takes place with the oxygen rather than the sulfur atoms of the ring where both are present. An exception (cf. Utimoto *et al.*⁷) is the addition of 1-pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ to conformationally locked 1,3-oxathianes; however, addition of methylolithium-YbCl₃ to all 1,3-oxathianes studied and of pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ to the conformationally mobile 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane proceeds 'normally'. Additions to 2-benzoylthiane are usually of low stereoselectivity and often proceed contrary to what would be predicted on the assumption that the organometallic reagent chelates with sulfur; an exception is methylmagnesium iodide which does follow Cram's chelate rule. The additions of RLi and RLi.YbCl₃ (R methyl or 1-pentynyl) to 2-benzoylthiane follow the same stereochemical course presumably proceeding contrary to Cram's chelate rule; thus the reversal observed with 1-pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ in the 1,3-oxathiane series appears not to be due to chelation with sulfur. The results with 2-methoxyacetylthiane suggest that chelation with the side-chain oxygen substituent prevails over chelation with the ring sulfur atom.

In previous publications^{1,2} we have discussed the use of 2-acyl-1,3-oxathianes, such as **1** (Scheme 1) in enantioselective synthesis. It is well established³ that the high diastereoselectivity of the addition of the Grignard reagent to **1** rests on Cram's chelate rule⁴, with coordination of the organometallic reagent with the oxathiane moiety occurring at oxygen rather than at sulfur, presumably because the oxygen site is a hard base coordinating with the hard organometallic reagent whereas the sulfur site is much softer⁵.

Scheme 1

It was the goal of the present work to examine the addition of organometallic reagents to analogs of **1** with a single oxygen or a single sulfur atom in the ring (2-acyloxanes and 2-acylthianes, **2,3**), shown in Scheme 2. Previous work⁶ had indicated that negligible stereoselectivity is observed in addition of organometallic reagents to a chiral 1,3-dithiane, 4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3-dithiane (**4**), the disulfur analog of **1**. However, it was not clear whether this was due to lack of coordination with sulfur or simply the fact that both the sulfur sites chelate nearly equally well. Our interest in this prob-

Scheme 2

lem was peaked by the observation of Utimoto *et al.*⁷ that the steric course of the addition of a lithium acetylide to **1** is reversed by the addition of certain rare earth salts, such as ytterbium trichloride, to the reaction mixture, with the possible implication that a softer metal, such as ytterbium, might chelate preferentially with sulfur rather than with oxygen.

Since our interest was in diastereoselectivity rather than asymmetric synthesis, the substrates used in this investigation were simple 2-acyloxanes or 2-acylthianes without additional substituents (Scheme 2; **2,3,7**). Since the previously examined 1,3-oxathianes (Scheme 1, see also Scheme 2; **6**) were conformationally biased, we also examined the reaction with an otherwise unsubstituted 2-acyl-1,3-oxathiane (**5**), the assumption in all cases being that the 2-acyl group in these substrates would be largely equatorial, i.e. that the compounds would be largely conformationally homogenous. With one possible exception, to be discussed later, the results with the simple 2-acyl-1,3-oxathiane **5** (as

[†]Dedicated to Professor Dhanonjay Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

compared to previous results with 1) bear out this assumption.

Synthesis :

In the oxathiane series, both the 2-benzoyl and 2-acetyl derivatives were obtained by the standard procedure² of adding an aldehyde to 2-lithio-1,3-oxathiane and then oxidizing the carbinol with Swern's reagent⁹. The synthesis of 2-acetyloxane has been described¹⁰ and two new syntheses of the known 2-benzoyloxane¹¹ are shown in Scheme 3. Scheme 4 displays the synthesis of 2-benzoylthiane. The synthesis of 7 is shown in Scheme 5.

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

Configuration of products :

Oxathiane series : Addition of methylmagnesium iodide to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (5) yielded, as the major isomer, a product with the carbinol proton at 4.94 ppm whereas addition of phenylmagnesium bromide to 2-acetyl-1,3-oxathiane yielded, as the major product, one whose

Scheme 5

carbinol proton signal was at 4.89 ppm. From earlier work with the 4,4,6-trimethyloxathianes⁸ the isomer with the higher-field proton is assigned the *R*,S** configuration at the carbinol center whereas the corresponding configuration of the other isomer is *R*,R**. In both cases the product is that predicted by Cram's chelate rule.

Fig. 1. (*R*,S**)-2-(1'-Hydroxy-1'-phenyl)-2'-hexynyl-1,3-oxathiane sulfone.

The configuration of the addition product of pentynyllithium to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane was confirmed to be the Cram chelate (*R*,S**) product by X-ray crystallography of the corresponding sulfone obtained by oxidation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. (*R*,S**)-2-(1'-Hydroxy-1'-phenyl)ethyloxane.

Oxane series : The product of addition of methylmagnesium chloride to 2-benzoyloxane was subjected to X-ray diffraction analysis and shown (Fig. 2) to be the R^*,S^* isomer, corresponding to addition according to Cram's chelate rule. The product of addition of phenylmagnesium bromide to 2-acetyloxane was shown by proton and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy to be the opposite diastereomer, R^*,R^* , also resulting from addition according to the chelate rule.

Thiane series : Since the major product of the addition

Fig. 3. (R^*,R^*)-2-(1'-Hydroxy-1'-phenyl)ethylthiane sulfone.

of dimethylcopperlithium to 2-benzoylthiane was noncrystalline, it (and the products of other additions yielding the same major diastereomer) was oxidized to the corresponding sulfone whose relative configuration was established, by X-ray crystallography, to be R^*,R^* (Fig. 3), corresponding to addition counter to Cram's chelate rule. The sole addition product of pentynyllithium to the same ketone was assumed to have the same configuration (R^*,R^*), also formed counter to Cram's chelate rule.

Other products : The products of addition of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CuLi}$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{Li}\cdot\text{YbCl}_3$ to 2-methoxyacetylthiane (see below)

Fig. 4. (R^*,R^*)-2-(1'-Hydroxy-1'-methyl-2'-methoxy)ethylthiane sulfone.

were combined, oxidized to the corresponding sulfone and subjected to X-ray crystallographic analysis (Fig. 4). The configuration of the product was found to be R^*,R^* , corresponding to addition not involving chelation with the ring sulfur.

Results

The results of the addition of various organometallic reagents to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (**5**) are shown in Table 1. Where data can be compared, the results are very similar to those reported earlier with the homologous trimethyl-1,3-oxathianes⁸. The addition of phenylmagnesium bromide in

Table 1. Additions of organometallics to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane

RM	Ratio of (R^*,S^*) to (R^*,R^*)
MeMgI	98.5 : 1.5
MeLi	89.4 : 10.6
Me ₂ CuLi	82 : 18
YbCl ₃ -MeLi	92 : 8
MeLi	82.5 : 17.5
PentynylLi	100 : 0
PentynylLi	100 : 0
YbCl ₃ -PentynylLi	96 : 4
YbCl ₃ -PentynylLi	73 : 27
YbCl ₃ -PentynylLi	100 : 0

diethyl ether to 2-acetyl-1,3-oxathiane at -20° gave 97% of the Cram chelate (R^*,R^*) product, again in good agreement with results in the 4,4,6-trimethyl homolog (92%)⁸.

Table 2. Additions of organometallics to bicyclic-2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane

RM	Ratio of (R^*,S^*) to (R^*,R^*)
MeMgI	99 : 1
MeLi	71 : 29
MeLi-YbCl ₃	65 : 35
1-PentynylLi	91 : 9 ^a
1-PentynylLi-YbCl ₃	6 : 94 ^a
1-PentynylLi-YCl ₃	6 : 94 ^a
1-PentynylLi	93 : 07 ^b
1-PentynylLi-YbCl ₃	0 : 100 ^b

^aAs reported in Ref. 7. ^bThis work.

Table 3. Additions of organometallics to *cis*-6-methyl-2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane

RM	Ratio of (<i>R</i> [*] , <i>S</i> [*]) to (<i>R</i> [*] , <i>R</i> [*])
MeMgCl	100 : 0
MeLi	64 : 36
YbCl ₃ -MeLi	59 : 41
Pentynylli	92 : 8
YbCl ₃ -Pentynylli	17 : 83

Surprisingly, we saw no reversal of the stereochemical course of addition with pentynyllithium-YbCl₃, although the results fluctuated rather widely (Table 2, 3 entries), perhaps because of irreproducibility of the reagent. Yet when we repeated the results of Utimoto *et al.*⁷ with the bicyclic oxathiane they employed, we obtained results essentially similar to theirs (Table 2). Believing that perhaps the difference might be between a monocyclic and a bicyclic 1,3-oxathiane, we synthesized 6-methyl-2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (6) and studied addition of organometallic reagents to it (Table 3). In this case, the reversal with pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ vs pentynyllithium does occur, suggesting that the simpler 1,3-oxathiane might possibly react in a ring-reversed form, i.e. with the benzoyl group axially disposed.

The results with 2-benzoyloxane are displayed in Table 4. Not surprisingly, all additions follow Cram's chelate rule, often with high stereoselectivity.

Table 4. Additions of organometallics to 2-benzoyloxane

RM	Ratio of (<i>R</i> [*] , <i>S</i> [*]) to (<i>R</i> [*] , <i>R</i> [*])
MeMgCl	100 : 0
MeLi	75 : 25
Me ₂ Mg	100 : 0
Me ₂ CuLi	76 : 24
YbCl ₃ -MeLi	96 : 4
Pentynylli	71 : 29
YbCl ₃ -Pentynylli	100 : 0

Table 5 displays the results of addition of various organometallic reagents to 2-benzoylthiane. In this case the stereoselectivity, except in the case of methylmagnesium iodide, is low for the Cram chelate product and in several instances (dimethylmagnesium, methylithium-YbCl₃, pentynyllithium, pentynyllithium-YbCl₃) there is substan-

tial preference for the nonchelated product. This is also true for dimethylcopperlithium where the reaction is quite sensitive to solvent.

Discussion

The results with the 2-acyloxanes (Table 4) support the earlier hypothesis that Cram's chelate rule dictates the composition of the products. In the case of the oxanes, there is essentially no competition to the chelation of the organometallic reagent with the oxygen atom of the ring. There is no reversal of stereochemical course with either methylithium-YbCl₃ or pentynyllithium-YbCl₃. A very different situation is observed with benzoylthianes (Table 5). Only methylmagnesium iodide (a relatively soft Grignard reagent?) shows evidence of strong complexing with sulfur. Other reagents are either poorly stereoselective or, as they become harder, actually display stereoselectivity opposite to Cram's chelate rule. It should be noted that the *R*^{*},*R*^{*} product is that predicted by the Felkin-Anh rule¹² which probably applies here in the absence of strong chelation.

The results in Table 5 seem to rule out the interpretation of the results of Utimoto *et al.*⁷ in terms of a 'reverse' che-

Table 5. Additions of organometallics to 2-benzoylthiane

RM	Ratio of (<i>R</i> [*] , <i>S</i> [*]) to (<i>R</i> [*] , <i>R</i> [*])
MeMgI	89 : 11
MeMgBr	68 : 32
MeMgBr + MgBr ₂	70 : 30
MeMgCl	64 : 36
MeLi	60 : 40
Me ₂ Mg	31 : 69
Me ₂ CuLi	9 : 91
YbCl ₃ -MeLi	11 : 89
Pentynylli	0 : 100
YbCl ₃ -Pentynylli	12 : 88

lation, i.e. chelation, in the presence of YbCl₃, with sulfur instead of oxygen in the 1,3-oxathiane in which the Japanese investigators observed a reversal of steric course. In this connection it is also to be noted that we did not see any reversal with methylithium-YbCl₃ compared to methylithium alone with any of the oxathianes studied (Tables 1-3). Possibly the reversal with the acetylenic reagent is due to complexation of YbCl₃ with the triple bond.

In earlier work¹³ we had seen competition of an alkoxy

group in the acyl substituent of a 2-acyl-1,3-oxathiane with the ring oxygen for chelation of the organometallic addend, resulting in diminished stereoselectivity in the addition. We therefore synthesized (Scheme 5) 2-methoxyacetylthiane and studied the addition of various organometallic reagents to it (Table 6). It is significant that in all cases involving addition of methyl nucleophiles, the predominant chelation was with the oxygen of the side-chain and not with the sulfur of the ring, as shown by X-ray crystallography. It would appear, by analogy, that this is also the case for pentynyllithium and for pentynyllithium-YbCl₃.

Table 6. Additions of organometallics to 2-methoxyacetylthiane

RM	Ratio of (R*,S*) to (R*,R*)
MeMgI	20 : 80
YbCl ₃ -MeLi	15 : 85
Me ₂ CuLi	15 : 85
PentynylLi	1 : 99
YbCl ₃ -PentynylLi	2 : 98

Experimental

2-(1'-Hydroxy-1'-phenyl)methylpentamethylene sulfoxides : To a solution of pentamethylene sulfoxide¹⁴ (13.27 g, 112.3 mmol, predried under vacuum) in THF (500 ml) at -78° was added *n*-BuLi (70.3 ml, 1.6 M in hexane, 12.3 mmol) dropwise, under argon. After stirring for 4.5 h at -78°, acid-free benzaldehyde (13.04 g, 112.3 mmol) dissolved in THF (200 ml) was added over 15 min. The mixture was stirred overnight and was allowed to warm up to room temperature. Water and saturated aqueous NH₄Cl were added to quench the reaction and ether was added to separate the layers. The ether layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with CHCl₃ (3×150 ml). The combined organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure to yield a creamy solid diastereomer mixture (23.61 g, 94%) (m.p. 130–135°); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.3 (5H, s), 5.5 (1H, d), 5.2 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz), 3.4 (1H, m), 2.6–3.0 (2H, m), 2.0 (1H, s), 1.0–1.80 (6H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 21.6, 22.7, 23.2, 24.1, 24.3, 24.9, 51.2, 51.3, 68.1, 68.5, 71.4, 74.4, 126.1, 127.1, 127.4, 128.0, 128.1, 128.2, 139.9, 141.4; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3250s, 1030s cm⁻¹ and others.

2-(1'-Hydroxy-1'-phenyl)methylthianes : To a solution of the above sulfoxides (3.0 g, 13.38 mmol) in THF (115 ml) under argon was added BH₃-THF complex (41 ml of a 1.0 M solution, 41 mmol) via syringe over 1 h. The mixture

was refluxed for 2 h before slow quenching with water and aqueous NaHCO₃. The solution was then extracted with ether and the organic layer dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. Flash column chromatography (silica gel, 30% ether/hexanes) gave diastereomeric 2-(1'-hydroxy-1'-phenyl)methylthianes (2.78 g, quantitative), m.p. 105–108°d (Found : C, 68.97; H, 7.73. C₁₂H₁₆OS calcd. for : C, 69.18; H, 7.74%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.3 (5H, s), 4.66 (1H, dd), 2.85–3.09 (1H, m), 2.40–2.80 (3H, m), 1.15–2.05 (6H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 24.0, 25.7, 26.9, 27.0, 28.6, 29.4, 49.3, 49.6, 75.2, 76.6, 126.5, 126.8, 127.8, 128.1, 128.2, 128.4, 141.4, 141.7; ν_{\max} (neat) 3600–3200s, 2000–1700w, 1600m, 1500s cm⁻¹ and others.

2-Benzoylthiane (3) : To a cold (-78°) solution of DMSO (0.49 g, 6.24 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (7 ml) under argon was added trifluoroacetic anhydride (0.89 ml, 6.3 mmol) dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (5 ml). After stirring for 45 min at -78°, 2-(1'-hydroxy-1'-phenyl)methylthiane (1.0 g, 4.8 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (25 ml) was added to this solution. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3.5 h at -78° and then triethylamine (3.0 ml, 1.5 mmol) was added. After warming to room temperature, the contents was poured into 10% aqueous HCl (100 ml). The two layers were separated and the organic layer was washed with aqueous NaHCO₃, dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. Flash column chromatography (silica gel, 10% ether/hexanes) gave white crystals (0.54 g, 54%), m.p. 68–68.5° (Found : C, 69.98; H, 6.91. C₁₂H₁₄OS calcd. for : C, 69.86; H, 6.84); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.9 (2H, m), 7.3 (3H, m), 4.38 (1H, dd), 2.70 (2H, t), 1.20–2.20 (6H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 23.9, 26.5, 28.3, 28.8, 44.7, 128.3, 128.4, 132.9, 135.2, 198.0; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1670s, 1040s cm⁻¹ and others.

Addition of methylmagnesium iodide to 2-benzoylthiane : MeMgI was prepared in the usual way, from Mg (120 mg, 5.0 mmol) and MeI (10 mmol) in a total of 12 ml diethyl ether. To this solution was added 2-benzoylthiane (206 mg, 1.0 mmol) dissolved in ether (10 ml) dropwise, via addition funnel. The resulting solution was refluxed for 0.5 h and then stirred at room temperature overnight. Saturated aqueous NH₄Cl, water and ether were added to quench and dilute the reaction mixture. After acidifying with 10% aqueous HCl, the solution was extracted with ether and the combined ether layers dried over Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure gave a mixture of diastereomers with little or no other chemical product in a ratio of 89 : 11 favoring the diastereomer with higher *R_f*.

Addition of methylmagnesium chloride and bromide to 2-benzoylthiane : In a dry flask under argon, MeMgCl

(0.833 ml of a 3.0 M solution in THF, 2.5 mmol) was diluted with ether (5.0 ml). To this solution at room temperature was added 2-benzoylthiane (103 mg in 5 ml ether, 0.5 mmol) via syringe followed by stirring for 2 h. Work-up as indicated for the MeMgI reaction above yielded the diastereomers in a 36 : 64 ratio. Similarly, addition of MeMgBr (1.5 M solution in 75 : 25 toluene : THF) yielded epimers in a ratio of 68 : 32 in favor of the diastereomer of higher R_f .

Reaction of 2-benzoylthiane with methylmagnesium bromide-magnesium bromide mixture : In a dry flask under argon, magnesium turning was placed and stirred dry for 15 min. To it were added THF (2 ml) and a drop of bromine. After stirring for 1 h a yellow precipitate was formed. Then MeMgBr (1.67 ml of a 1.5 M 75 : 25 toluene : THF solution, 2.5 mmol) was added via syringe followed by stirring for 15 min. The color of the solution disappeared and some unreacted Mg was left. After the addition of more THF (3 ml) to this solution, 2-benzoylthiane was added via syringe and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. Saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were added and the resulting two phase solution was stirred for 1 h to dissolve all salts. The phases were separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined ether layers were dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure to give the diastereomeric carbinols in a ratio of 70 : 30, favoring the isomer of higher R_f .

Addition of methyllithium to 2-benzoylthiane : To MeLi (1.92 ml, 1.3 M in ether, 2.5 mmol) in a dry flask, diluted with ether (5 ml), was added 2-benzoylthiane (103 mg dissolved in 5 ml ether, 0.5 mmol) via syringe at -78° . After stirring for 3 h and allowing the reaction mixture to warm up to room temperature slowly, saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were added. Work-up as above yielded the two diastereomeric products in a 60 : 40 ratio, favoring the isomer of higher R_f .

Addition of dimethylmagnesium to 2-benzoylthiane : To dimethylmagnesium (2 ml of a 1.0 M solution in THF, 2.0 mmol) in a dry flask, diluted with THF (5 ml), was added 2-benzoylthiane (103 mg, 0.5 mmol, dissolved in 5 ml THF) via syringe at -78° . The mixture was stirred overnight by allowing it slowly warm up to room temperature. Saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were then added and the resulting two-phase solution was stirred for 1 h. Work-up as described above yielded the two diastereomers in a 31 : 69 ratio favoring the one of lower R_f .

Addition of dimethylcopperlithium to 2-benzoylthiane : To CuI (476 mg, 2.5 mmol) suspended in THF (5.0 ml) was added MeLi (3.57 ml of a 1.4 M solution in ether, 5.0

mmol) via syringe, under argon, at -78° . The resulting suspension was stirred for 30 min, then 2-benzoylthiane (103 mg dissolved in 5 ml THF, 0.5 mmol) was added via syringe. After stirring for 3 h at -78° , the solution was allowed to warm to room temperature. Saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were then added. Work-up as above gave a mixture of diastereomeric carbinols in a 9 : 91 ratio favoring the one of lower R_f .

Addition of methyllithium-YbCl₃ to 2-benzoylthiane : To a suspension of anhydrous YbCl_3 (520 mg, 2.5 mmol) in THF (5.0 ml) was added MeLi (1.78 ml of a 1.4 M ether solution, 2.5 mmol) via syringe, under argon, at -78° . The first two drops of MeLi changed the color of the reaction to pink-red, after further addition it became green. After stirring for 0.5 h at -78° , 2-benzoylthiane (103 mg, 0.5 mmol, dissolved in 5 ml THF) was added to this solution dropwise via syringe. The mixture was then stirred overnight while allowing it to slowly warm up to room temperature. The reaction was quenched with a saturated aqueous NH_4Cl solution and water and was diluted with ether. Work-up, as described above yielded the diastereomeric carbinol mixture in a 11 : 89 ratio, favoring the diastereomer of lower R_f .

Determination of the relative configuration of the diastereomers :

Below are the typical ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of a crude reaction mixture of the diastereomers obtained from the addition of methyl nucleophiles to 2-benzoylthiane : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.21–7.50 (5H, m), [1H, (3.17*, 3.14* dd, 3.14, 3.11 dd)], 2.55–2.78 (2H, m), 2.32 (1H, br), 1.12–2.01 (6H, m), [1.65, 1.58* (3H, s)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 25.9*, 26.5*, 26.8*, 26.9, 28.5, 28.6, 29.4, 28.7*, 29.5*, 54.5, 54.8*, 76.1, 76.2*, 125.2, 125.4*, 126.8, 127.1*, 128.0, 128.0*, 145.8, 146.2* (signals marked with an asterisk correspond to the lower R_f diastereomer).

In order to determine the relative configuration of the diastereomers, a pure sample of the lower R_f diastereomer was obtained by flash column chromatography (silica gel, 20% ether/hexanes) and was oxidized to the sulfone as follows. The pure diastereomer of lower R_f (50 mg, 0.23 mmol) was dissolved in a 1 : 1 mixture of THF-ethanol (2.4 ml). To it was added monoperoxyphthalic acid magnesium salt hexahydrate powder (652 mg, 0.91 mmol) and the mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. Saturated aqueous NaHCO_3 and ether were then added. The resulting two-phase solution was stirred for 1 h and the phases were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether and the combined organic layers was dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. Flash column chromatography (silica gel, 60% ether/hexane) gave sulfone (43

mg) : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.22–7.51 (5H, m), 3.19 (1H, d), 2.85–3.07 (2H, m), 1.20–2.20 (6H, m), 1.84 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR δ 24.3, 25.1, 25.9, 27.2, 54.3, 71.0, 76.5, 125.8, 127.8, 128.3, 144.4. The single crystal X-ray analysis of this sample (Fig. 3) showed its configuration to be R^*,R^* (it may be noted that the Ortep projection of the racemate shows the equivalent S,S) corresponding to non-chelate addition.

Addition of pentynyllithium to 2-benzoylthiane : To a solution of 1-pentyne (0.123 mmol) in THF (2.5 ml), was added MeLi (0.893 ml of a 1.4 M solution in ether, 1.25 mmol) at -78° followed by stirring for 45 min. To this solution was added 2-benzoylthiane (52 mg, 0.25 mmol, dissolved in 2.5 ml THF) via syringe. After stirring for 6 h and allowing the reaction mixture to warm to room temperature slowly, saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were added. The aqueous layer was extracted (three times) with ether and the combined organic layers dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated at reduced pressure. NMR analysis of the crude sample indicated the formation of the product as a single diastereomer : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.68 (2H, m), 7.38 (3H, m), 3.10 (1H, dd, J 10.6, 2.6 Hz), 3.07 (1H, br), 2.75 (1H, m), 2.64 (1H, m), 2.32 (2H, t), 1.72–1.94 (3H, m), 1.53–1.71 (4H, m), 1.25 (1H, m), 1.06 (3H, t); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 142.6, 127.8, 126.3, 88.1, 80.7, 75.5, 55.6, 29.1(2C), 26.7, 25.7, 22.0, 20.7, 13.5.

Addition of pentynyllithium- YbCl_3 to 2-benzoylthiane : To a solution of 1-pentyne (0.123 ml, 1.25 mmol) in THF (2.5 ml), was added MeLi (0.893 ml of a 1.4 M solution in ether, 1.25 mmol) at -78° followed by stirring for 30 min. This solution was transferred onto dry anhydrous YbCl_3 and stirred for an additional 45 min at -78° . To this suspension was added 2-benzoylthiane (52 mg, 0.25 mmol, dissolved in 2.5 ml THF) via syringe. After stirring for 6 h and allowing the reaction mixture to warm up to room temperature slowly, dilute aqueous HCl, water and ether were added. It was worked-up as described above. The proton NMR of the crude sample indicated a diastereomer ratio of 12 : 88 favoring the same diastereomer as obtained in the pentynyllithium addition : ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) δ 7.62–7.69 (2H, m), 7.26–7.40 (3H, m), [1H, 3.16* (dd, 11.2, 2.4 Hz), 3.08 (dd, 10.8, 2.8 Hz)], 3.05 (1H, br), 2.57–2.77 (2H, m), 2.32 (2H, t), 1.72–1.94 (3H, m), 1.52–1.70 (4H, m), 1.15–1.32 (1H, m), 1.05 (3H, t); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 142.6, 127.8, 127.7*, 126.3, 126.1*, 88.1, 87.5*, 80.7, 81.5*, 75.5, 75.1*, 55.6, 54.5*, 29.1(2C), 29.5*, 28.4*, 26.7, 26.6*, 25.7, 25.9*, 22.0, 20.7, 13.5 (asterisked signals belong to minor diastereomer).

2-Acetyloxane : It was prepared as described by Gouin¹⁰

from 3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran via 2-chlorotetrahydropyran and 2-ethynyltetrahydropyran, b.p. 35–40°/21 mm (lit.¹⁰ 87°/32 mm). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.1–2.1 (6H, m), 2.17 (3H, s), 3.28–3.62 (1H, m), 3.65–3.86 (1H, m), 3.9–4.16 (1H, m); ν_{max} (neat) 2940s, 2750s, 1725s, 1440m, 1420m, 1355s, 1200s, 1168s, 1090s, 1045s, 895s cm^{-1} .

*Addition of phenylmagnesium bromide to 2-acetyloxane*¹⁰ : Addition of 2-acetyloxane in diethyl ether to a phenylmagnesium bromide solution under reflux yielded, according to ^1H -NMR, one isomer, 100% d.e. : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.22–1.48 (5H, m), 1.46 (3H, s), 1.7–1.9 (1H, m), 3.21 (1H, br s), 3.21–3.41 (2H, m), 4.02 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz), 7.2–7.5 (5H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 23.3, 25.5, 25.7, 27.4, 66.7, 75.7, 84.1, 125.7, 126.7, 127.6, 145.7.

Tetrahydropyran-2-carboxylic acid : 3,4-Dihydro-2H-pyran-2-carboxylic acid sodium salt (100 g, 66.62 mmol) in 90% ethanol (135 ml) was hydrogenated over 5% palladium on charcoal for 3 h at 40 psi using a Parr apparatus. Celite was added and the mixture was filtered. The solution was concentrated at reduced pressure to half of its original volume. It was then poured into 10% aqueous HCl (100 ml) and extracted with ether (3×25 ml). The combined organic layers was dried (MgSO_4) and concentrated to give one single product detected by GLC (10% SE-30 Chromosorb column), (7.41 g, 85%), b.p. 144–146°/25 mm (lit.¹¹ 144–147°/24 mm); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.40–2.20 (6H, m), 3.36–3.80 (1H, m), 3.96–4.32 (2H, m), 10.30 (1H, s).

Phenyl 2-tetrahydropyranyl thioether : To 3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran (10.0 ml, 109.6 mmol) dissolved in THF (220 ml) at 0° was added HBr (4.1 ml of 48% solution, 36.5 mmol). The solution was stirred for 0.5 h at 0° and then 1 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-water bath and thiophenol (11.2 ml, 109.6 mmol) was added dropwise via syringe. After stirring overnight, saturated aqueous Na_2CO_3 and ether were added. The phases were separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined ether layers was washed with 10% aqueous NaOH and water, dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated at reduced pressure. Drying under full vacuum overnight gave the desired product as oil (21.1 g); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.38–7.58 (2H, m), 7.12–7.30 (3H, m), 5.15–5.25 (1H, dd), 4.09–4.23 ((1H, m), 3.52–3.65 (1H, m), 1.40–2.10 (6H, m); ^{13}C nmr (CDCl_3) δ 21.5, 25.3, 31.4, 64.3, 85.1, 126.5, 128.6, 130.7, 135.2.

Phenyl-2-tetrahydropyranylcarbinol : Naphthalene (1.63 g, 13.0 mmol, dissolved in 5 ml THF) was added to a suspension of lithium metal pieces (*ca* 1 g, excess) in THF (51 ml), under argon, at -78° , which was then stirred for

0.5 h. To the resulting solution at -78° , was added phenyl 2-tetrahydropyranyl thioether (5.00 g, 25.5 mmol, dissolved in 10 ml THF) via syringe and stirred for 3.5 h. This was followed by the dropwise addition of neat benzaldehyde (2.6 ml, 25.51 mmol) and stirring overnight, while warming to room temperature. The solution was transferred to a different flask via cannula under argon leaving the unreacted lithium pieces behind. Saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were added to the solution and the phases were separated. Work-up as described in the previous experiment followed by flash column chromatography (30% ether/hexanes) gave carbinol (4.71 g) as a mixture of diastereomers: ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.2–7.5 (5H, m), 4.80 (1H, d), 4.05 (1H, d), 3.40–3.55 (2H, m), 1.80 (1H, br), 1.20–1.65 (6H, m), ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 22.9, 24.1, 26.0, 68.9, 75.8, 81.1, 126.4, 127.3, 128.1, 140.3.

2-Benzoyloxane (2) : (a) To a solution of DMSO (4.6 ml, 64.2 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (128 ml) in a dry flask was added neat oxalyl chloride (5.6 ml, 64.2 mmol) via syringe at -78° . After stirring for 0.5 h at -78° , phenyl-2-tetrahydropyranylcarbinol (6.17 g, 32.1 mmol) dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (32 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h and then triethylamine (17.9 ml, 128.4 mmol) was added. The dry ice-acetone bath was removed and water and 10% aqueous HCl were added. The phases were separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined organic layers was washed with 10% aqueous HCl and then with water, dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. Flash column chromatography (15% ether/hexanes) gave 2-benzoyloxane as a clear oil (5.85 g, 96%), b.p. 100–102 $^{\circ}$ /0.5 mm (lit.¹⁴ 170–171 $^{\circ}$ /26 mm); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.83 (2H, m), 7.25–7.55 (3H, m), 4.62 (1H, m), 3.95–4.15 (1H, m), 3.40–3.58 (1H, m), 1.41–1.90 (6H, m); ^{13}C nmr (CDCl_3) δ 23.1, 25.5, 28.9, 68.6, 79.7, 128.5, 128.8, 133.2, 134.9, 198.0; ν_{max} (CCl_4) 3500w, 2950s, 2850s, 1705s, 1610m, 1500w, 1460w, 1100s cm^{-1} .

(b) To a cold (0°) solution of tetrahydropyran-2-carboxylic acid (3.0 g, 23.06 mmol) in anhydrous diethyl ether (23 ml), under nitrogen, was added, dropwise, a 2 M benzene-ether solution (23.5 ml) of phenyllithium (47 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0° and an additional 4 h at room temperature and then poured into a mixture of crushed ice and 10% aqueous HCl with vigorous stirring (5 min). The organic portion was washed with saturated aqueous Na_2CO_3 , dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 and concentrated. Purification by flash column chromatography (15% EtOAc/Hex) gave the desired ketone (2.30 g, 50% yield), b.p. 100–102 $^{\circ}$ /0.5 mm, identical with the material obtained as above.

Addition of methylmagnesium chloride to 2-benzoyloxane

oxane : To MeMgCl (1.67 ml of a 3.0 M solution in THF, 5.0 mmol) plus ether (10 ml) under argon at room temperature was added 2-benzoyloxane (190 mg, 1.0 mmol, in 10 ml ether) via syringe. After stirring for 2 h, the reaction was quenched with saturated aqueous NH_4Cl and ether was added. After stirring for an additional 1 h, the phases were separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined organic layers was dried over Na_2SO_4 and then concentrated at reduced pressure to yield a single diastereomer in quantitative yield as a white solid. In order to determine the absolute stereochemistry of this diastereomer, a sample was recrystallized from hexanes and subjected to the single crystal X-ray structure analysis (Fig. 2): ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.19–7.48 (5H, m), 4.08 (1H, br d), 3.30–3.56 (2H, m), 2.98 (1H, br), 1.0–1.80 (6H, m), 1.60 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 23.3, 25.2, 26.0, 27.7, 69.0, 75.5, 83.8, 125.3, 126.5, 127.9, 144.9.

Addition of dimethylmagnesium to 2-benzoyloxane : To 2.5 ml of dimethylmagnesium (2.5 ml, 1.0 M in THF, 2.5 mmol), diluted with THF (5 ml) and cooled to -78° was added 2-benzoyloxane (120 mg, 0.63 mmol, dissolved in 5 ml THF) via syringe. The reaction mixture was quenched and worked up as described in the preceding procedure to give exclusively the same diastereomer obtained from MeMgCl addition, as shown by ^1H nmr.

Addition of methyllithium to 2-benzoyloxane : In a dry flask, MeLi (1.92 ml, 1.3 M ether solution, 2.5 mmol) was diluted with ether (5 ml). To it at -78° , was added 2-benzoyloxane (95 mg, 0.5 mmol, dissolved in 5 ml ether) via syringe. After stirring for 3 h and allowing the reaction mixture to warm up to room temperature slowly, saturated aqueous NH_4Cl and water were added and worked-up as described above. The proton NMR of the crude product indicated a 75 : 25 ratio of diastereomers favoring the one with the higher R_f value described above.

Addition of methyllithium-YbCl₃ to 2-benzoyloxane : The reagent was prepared as described for 3. After stirring for 0.5 h at -78° , 2-benzoyloxane (95 mg, 0.5 mmol, dissolved in 5 ml THF) was added dropwise via syringe. The mixture was stirred overnight while allowing it to slowly warm up to room temperature. It was worked up as described above to give the diastereomeric carbinols in a 96 : 4 ratio favoring the higher R_f diastereomer. The major product was the same diastereomer produced in the MeMgCl and Me_2Mg additions as evidenced by ^1H NMR.

Addition of dimethylcopperlithium to 2-benzoyloxane : To a suspension of CuI (476 mg, 2.5 mmol) in THF (5.0 ml) at -78° was added MeLi (3.57 ml of 1.4 M ether solution, 5.0 mmol) via syringe, under argon. The resulting sus-

pension was stirred for 30 min, then 2-benzoyloxane (95 mg, 0.5 mmol, dissolved in 5 ml THF) was added via syringe. After stirring for 3 h at -78° , saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were added followed by work-up as described above to give the diastereomeric carbinols in 76 : 24 ratio favoring the higher R_f diastereomer.

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium to 2-benzoyloxane : To a solution of 1-pentyne (0.246 ml, 2.50 mmol) in THF (5.0 ml), was added *n*-BuLi (1.82 ml of a 1.4 M solution in hexanes, 2.55 mmol) at -78° and the solution was stirred for 45 min. To this solution was added 2-benzoyloxane (95 mg, 0.50 mmol, dissolved in 5.0 ml ether) via syringe. The solution became yellow-orange. After stirring for 3 h and allowing the reaction mixture to warm up to room temperature slowly, saturated aqueous NH_4Cl , water and ether were added followed by work-up as described above. The proton NMR of the crude product indicated a 71 : 29 ratio of diastereomers favoring the sole diastereomer produced by pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ addition (see below) : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.10–7.70 (5H, m), [4.06, 3.96* (1H, br d)], 3.20–3.75 (2H, m), 0.7–2.4 (13H, m), [*refers to minor diastereomer].

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ to 2-benzoyloxane : To a solution of 1-pentyne (0.123 ml, 1.25 mmol) in THF (2.5 ml), was added *n*-BuLi (0.912 ml of a 1.4 M solution in hexanes, 1.28 mmol) at -78° with stirring for 30 min. This solution was transferred onto dry anhydrous YbCl₃ (260 mg, 1.25 mmol) and stirred for an additional 45 min at -78° . The solution became dark pink-red. To this solution was added 2-benzoyloxane (48 mg, 0.25 mmol, dissolved in 2.5 ml THF) via syringe. After stirring for 3 h and allowing the reaction mixture to warm up to room temperature slowly, dilute HCl, water and ether were added. The phases were separated and the aqueous layer was twice extracted with ether. The combined organic layers was dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated at reduced pressure. The proton NMR of the crude sample indicated the formation of a single diastereomer : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.20–7.70 (5H, m), 4.11 (1H, br d), 3.35–3.80 (3H, m), 0.69–2.49 (13H, m).

2-(1'-Hydroxy-1'-phenyl)methyl-1,3-oxathianes : To a cold (-78°) solution of 1,3-oxathiane¹⁵ (20 g, 19.23 mmol) in dry THF (26 ml) was added dropwise under nitrogen, 1.3 M *sec*-BuLi (32 ml, 41.6 mmol) in cyclohexane. After stirring for 3.5 h, a solution of benzaldehyde (2.12 g, 20 mmol) in THF was added dropwise at -78° . The reaction mixture was stirred for an additional 20 min and then quenched with saturated aqueous NH_4Cl (20 ml) and water (20 ml). The resulting mixture was extracted with ether and the combined

organic layers was dried over MgSO_4 and then concentrated. Flash column chromatography (30% EtOAc/hexanes) gave the desired product (2.23 g, 55%) as a mixture of diastereomers, m.p. 80 – 90° : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.5–2.20 (2H, m), 2.52–3.08 (2H, m), 3.38 (1H, br s), 3.60 (2H, dt, J 3, 12 Hz), 4.21 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz), 4.71 (1H, dd, J 6.4, 10 Hz), 7.32 (5H, s); ν_{max} (neat) 3450s, 2980s, 2910s, 2860s, 1600s, 1450m, 1420w, 1280m, 1200s, 1070s, 1000m, 950w cm^{-1} .

2-Benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (5) : To a cold (-78°) solution of DMSO (0.59 g, 7.55 mmol) in 5 ml of dry CH_2Cl_2 under nitrogen was added trifluoroacetic anhydride (1.64 g, 7.55 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (4 ml). After stirring for 0.5 h at -78° , 2-(1'-hydroxy-1'-phenyl)methyl-1,3-oxathiane (0.72 g, 3.43 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (8 ml) was added to this solution. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h at -78° and then triethylamine (2.0 ml, 13.7 mmol) was added. After warming up 0° , the contents was poured into 10% aqueous HCl (20 ml) and agitated. The organic layer was separated, washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 , dried over MgSO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. Flash column chromatography (silica gel, 25% EtOAc/hexanes) gave the desired ketone (0.58 g, 78%), m.p. 81.5 – 82° (Found : C, 63.20; H, 5.87. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ calcd. for : C, 63.19; H, 6.17%); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.70–2.35 (2H, m), 2.74–3.02 (1H, dt, J 4, 13 Hz), 3.04–3.40 (1H, dt, J 3.5, 13 Hz), 3.70 (1H, dt, J 3, 11 Hz), 4.32 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz), 6.13 (1H, s), 7.40–7.62 (3H, m), 8.02–8.18 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 25.6, 28.2, 69.8, 83.5, 128.4, 129.3, 133.6, 133.8, 192.5; ν_{max} (neat) 3060m, 2960s, 2910s, 2860s, 1690s, 1600s, 1440m, 1435m, 1260m, 1200s, 1070m, 1015w cm^{-1} .

2-(1'-Hydroxy)ethyl-1,3-oxathianes : These were prepared as the above 1-benzyl analogs substituting acetaldehyde for benzaldehyde. Flash column chromatography (30% EtOAc/hexanes) gave the desired product (1.82 g, 76%) as a mixture of carbinols : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ [1.20 (3H, d, J 3 Hz), 1.26* (3H, d, J 3 Hz)], 1.60–2.23 (2H, m), 2.67–3.24 (2H, m), 3.33 (1H, br s), 3.50–4.00 (2H, m), 4.24 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz), [4.61 (1H, d, J 7 Hz), 4.79* (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 18.3, 25.9, 26.1, 27.3, 27.4, 69.4, 69.6, 69.9, 70.2, 87.5, 87.5, 87.8; ν_{max} (neat) 3450s, 2980s, 2910s, 2860s, 1430m, 1375m, 1280s, 1150m, 1100s cm^{-1} and others (asterisked signals are of minor isomer).

2-Acetyl-1,3-oxathiane : It was prepared by the same procedure (Swern oxidation) as 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane. The yield was 40% after purification (flash column chromatography, 30% EtOAc/hexanes) : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.60–2.20 (2H, m), 2.31 (3H, s), 2.70–3.34 (2H, m), 3.56–3.88 (1H, dt, J 3, 10 Hz), 4.32 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz), 5.40

(1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 25.4, 25.7, 27.8, 69.6, 85.3, 203.5; ν_{max} (neat) 2960, 2910, 2850, 1730, 1625, 1420 cm^{-1} and others.

Addition of phenylmagnesium bromide to 2-acetyl-1,3-oxathiane: Addition of 2-acetyl-1,3-oxathiane to a cold (-20°) ether solution of phenylmagnesium bromide (cf. Ref. 8) gave a mixture of carbinols in a 97.7 : 2.3 ratio, according to ^1H nmr : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.21–1.98 (2H, m), 1.62 (3H, s), 2.20 (1H, s), 2.69 (1H, br, d, J 12 Hz), 2.91 (1H, td, J 3, 12 Hz), 3.57 (1H, td, J 3, 12 Hz), 4.15 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz), [4.89 (1H, s), 4.93* (1H, s)], 7.2–7.5 (5H, m) (asterisked signal is of minor isomer).

Addition of methylmagnesium iodide to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane: Addition of 2-benzoylthiane to an ether solution of methylmagnesium iodide similarly gave the same carbinols but in a 1.5 : 98.5 ratio : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.21–2.02 (2H, m), 1.61 (3H, s), 2.68 (1H, d td, J 15, 3, 1.5 Hz), 2.92 (1H, td, J 13.4, 3 Hz), 2.95 (1H, s), 3.62 (1H, td J 12, 2.4 Hz), 4.30 (1H, br d, J 12 Hz), [4.89* (1H, s), 4.94 (1H, s)], 7.2–7.5 (5H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 25.5, 26.8, 27.6, 70.6, 75.7, 90.3, 125.2, 127.2, 127.7, 148.0 (*signal of minor isomer).

Addition on methyllithium to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane: The reaction of MeLi (0.892 ml of 1.4 M ether solution, 1.25 mmol) and 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (52 mg, 0.25 mmol, dissolved in 2.5 ml ether) was carried out as described for 2-benzoylthiane above. The proton NMR of the crude sample indicated a 83 : 17 ratio of diastereomers favoring the same diastereomer produced by the MeLi- YbCl_3 addition reaction (see below).

Addition of methyllithium- YbCl_3 to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane: To dry, anhydrous YbCl_3 (260 mg, 1.25 mmol) was added MeLi (0.892 ml of 1.4 M ether solution, 1.25 mmol) at -78° followed by stirring for 45 min. To this solution at -78° was added 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (52 mg, 0.25 mmol, dissolved in 2.5 ml ether) via syringe. After stirring for 3 h and allowing the reaction mixture to warm to room temperature slowly, dilute aqueous HCl and water were added. The aqueous layer was twice extracted with ether. The combined organic layers was dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The proton NMR of the crude sample showed a 92 : 8 ratio of diastereomers : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.26–7.68 (5H, m), [4.94, 4.88* (1H, s)], 4.22–4.30 (1H, m), 3.65 (1H, t), 2.90 (1H, t), 2.92 (1H, br), 2.63–2.73 (1H, m), 1.85–2.0 (1H, m), 1.64 (3H, s), 1.59–1.68 (1H, m) (*signal of minor diastereomer).

Addition of dimethylcopperlithium to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane: The reaction was carried out essentially as described for 2-benzoyloxane above. The diastereomeric

carbinols were obtained in a 82 : 18 ratio as shown by NMR, the major isomer being the same as for MeLi addition.

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium- YbCl_3 to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane: The procedure was the same as described for 2-benzoyloxane above. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of the crude sample indicated the formatin of a single diastereomer, the same as formed in the absence of YbCl_3 (see below) : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.65 (2H, m), 7.32 (3H, m), 4.99 (1H, s), 4.27 (1H, m), 3.65 (1H, dt, J 12, 2 Hz), 3.25 (1H, br), 2.91 (1H, dt, J 13, 2.7 Hz), 2.71 (1H, d), 2.27 (2H, t), 1.86–2.04 (1H, m), 1.45–1.70 (3H, m), 1.00 (3H, t); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 13.4, 20.8, 21.9, 25.6, 27.8, 70.8, 74.2, 81.2, 86.6, 90.4, 126.2, 127.8, 128.0, 140.3.

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane: The reaction was carried out essentially as described for 2-benzoyloxane above and gave a single diastereomer, identical with the one obtained in the presence of YbCl_3 , as shown by ^1H NMR.

Oxidation of pentynyllithium addition product: The product of pentynyllithium addition to 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (70 mg, 0.25 mmol) was dissolved in acetone (2.5 ml) and stirred with H_2O_2 (0.071 ml of 30% solution, 0.63 mmol) for 6 h at 0° . Monoperoxyphthalic acid magnesium salt hexahydrate (250 mg, 0.50 mmol) and two drops of glacial acetic acid were then added and the resulting mixture was stirred for 8 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by flash column chromatography over silica gel equipped with a pad of K_2CO_3 on top of the column. Purification yielded (60 mg, 78%) of the desired sulfone : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 7.70 (2H, m), 7.35 (3H, m), 5.10 (1H, s), 4.18 (1H, m), 3.4–3.65 (2H, m), 3.13–3.32 (2H, m), 2.46–2.61 (1H, m), 2.32 (2H, t), 2.07–2.17 (1H, m), 1.62 (2H, m), 1.02 (3H, t); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 13.4, 20.8, 21.7, 25.3, 52.0, 68.6, 72.4, 78.5, 89.7, 98.1, 126.3, 127.9, 128.3, 140.5. From X-ray analysis, the structure of this diastereomer (Fig. 1) was established as the Cram product arising from chelation to oxygen.

6-Methyl-2-benzoyloxathiane (6): It was prepared in two steps as described for 2-benzoyloxathiane above, but on a smaller scale, starting from 6-methyl-1,3-oxathiane¹⁶ (1.87 g, 15.85 mmol). Flash column chromatography of the crude product yielded a clear oil (1.38 g, 39% for two steps) : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 8.10 (2H, d), 7.58 (1H, t), 7.45 (2H, t), 6.11 (1H, s), 3.78 (1H, m), 3.23 (1H, td), 2.92 (1H, dt), 1.69–1.91 (2H, m), 1.32 (3H, d); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 22.2, 28.8, 32.3, 76.8, 84.8, 128.4, 129.6, 133.7, 133.9, 192.5.

Addition of methylmagnesium chloride to 6-methyl-2-

benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (6) : To MeMgCl (0.383 ml of 3 M solution in THF, 1.15 mmol) in THF (2.3 ml) was added 6-methyl-2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane (50 mg, 0.23 mmol, dissolved in 2.3 ml of THF) via syringe at 0°. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h while allowing it to reach room temperature slowly and worked up as indicated for similar reactions above. ¹H and ¹³C NMR of the crude sample indicated the presence of only one diastereomer. Repeating the same reaction at room temperature gave the same product : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.25–7.80 (5H, m), 4.96 (1H, s), 3.61–3.65 (1H, m), 2.85 (1H, 3d), 2.82 (1H, br), 2.71 (1H, dt), 1.45–1.74 (2H, m), 1.66 (3H, s), 1.25 (3H, d); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 22.2, 27.1, 27.9, 32.3, 75.7, 76.7, 90.4, 125.3, 127.3, 128.0, 143.6.

Addition of methyllithium to 6 : The reaction was carried out as described for 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane above. The proton NMR of the crude sample indicated a 64 : 36 ratio of diastereomers favoring the same isomer produced in the MeMgCl addition reaction : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.25–7.60 (5H, m), [4.96, 4.87* (1H, s)], 3.55–3.70 (1H, m), 2.85–2.95 (1H, 3d), 2.65–2.78 (1H, 3t), 1.45–1.78 (2H, m), [1.66, 1.64* (3H, s)], [1.25, 1.19* (3H, d)] (peaks marked with an asterisk belong to the minor diastereomer).

Addition of methyllithium-YbCl₃ to 6 : The reaction was carried out as described for 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane. The proton NMR of the crude sample indicated a 59 : 41 ratio of diastereomers favoring the same diastereomer produced by the MeMgCl addition.

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium to 6 : The reaction was carried out as described for 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane. The proton NMR of the crude sample indicated approximately 92 : 8 ratio of diastereomers favoring the opposite diastereomer obtained from pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ addition (see below) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.70 (2H, m), 7.38 (3H, m), [5.03, 4.82* (1H, s)], 3.62–3.80 (1H, m), 3.51 (1H, br), 2.70–3.01 (2H, m), 2.30 (2H, t), 1.20–1.81 (4H, m), 1.30 (3H, d), 1.05 (3H, t), (*belongs to minor diastereomer).

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ to 6 : The reaction was carried out as described for 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane. The proton NMR spectrum of the crude product indicated the formation of diastereomeric carbinols in 13 : 87 ratio as shown by the prevalence of the 4.81 ppm over the 5.02 ppm signal.

Addition of methyllithium to 1¹⁷ : The reaction was carried out essentially as described for 2-benzoylthiane above. Proton NMR of the crude sample indicated a 71 : 29 ratio of diastereomers favoring the Cram chelate rule isomer : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.25–7.60 (5H, m), [5.12, 5.05* (1H, s)], 3.34–3.60 (1H, m), 2.88 (1H, br), 0.80–2.05 (20H, m) (*be-

longs to minor diastereomer).

Addition of methyllithium-YbCl₃ to 1 : The reaction was carried out essentially as described for 2-benzoyl-1,3-oxathiane. The proton NMR spectrum of the crude sample indicated a 66 : 34 ratio of diastereomers favoring the same isomer produced in the methyllithium addition.

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium to 1 : The reaction was carried out essentially as described for 2-benzoyloxane. The proton NMR spectrum of the crude sample indicated the presence of the diastereomers in a 93 : 7 ratio. Comparison with literature data suggests that the *R*,S** ('chelate') isomer predominates : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.22–7.80 (5H, m), [5.14, 4.95* (1H, s)], 3.50 (1H, m), 0.74–2.35 (24H, m) (*belongs to minor diastereomer).

Addition of 1-pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ to 1 : The reaction was carried out essentially as described for 2-benzoylthiane. The proton NMR spectrum of the crude sample indicated the formation of a single diastereomer which is the opposite of the major diastereomer obtained from pentynyllithium addition. Comparison with literature and previous data indicated the structure of this diastereomer as the 'non-chelate' product (*R*,R**) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.22–7.80 (5H, m), 4.95 (1H, s), 4.30 (1H, 3d), 3.00 (1H, br), 2.30 (2H, t), 0.74–2.25 (22H, m).

2-Methoxyacetylpentamethylene sulfoxides : To a solution of pentamethylenesulfoxide¹⁴ (1.54 g, 13.05 mmol) in THF (26 ml) at –78°, under argon, was added *n*-BuLi (6.26 ml of 2.5 M solution in hexanes, 15.66 mmol) with stirring for 2.5 h, followed by addition of neat ethyl methoxyacetate (1.54 g, 13.05 mmol). After the reaction mixture was stirred overnight and allowed to warm up to room temperature, saturated aqueous NH₄Cl and ether were added. Two phases were separated and the aqueous layer was extracted twice with ether and three times with chloroform. The combined organic layers was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. Purification by flash column chromatography yielded *cis*- and *trans*-2-methoxyacetylpentamethylene sulfoxides (1.85 g, 75%), ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 4.12 (2H, 2AB), [3.68 (dd), 3.60 (dd), 1H], 3.33 (3H, s), 2.00 (1H, td), [2.65 (dt), 2.52 (dt), 1H], 2.00–2.33 (2H, m), 1.80–1.91 (1H, m), 1.52–1.75 (2H, m), 1.30–1.45 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ [203.8, 202.4], [78.3, 76.9], [63.3, 59.2], [51.1, 46.9], 24.7, 23.5, 21.4, 17.6, 15.4 (bracketed peaks belong to different diastereomers).

2-Methoxyacetylthiane (7) : Triphenylphosphine (1.02 g, 3.88 mmol) and iodine (0.49 g, 3.88 mmol) were stirred in acetonitrile (3 ml) for 0.5 h. The resulting yellow slurry, at room temperature, was added a mixture of sulfoxides (0.59

g, 3.10 mmol, dissolved in 3.1 ml of acetonitrile) and KI (0.77 g, 4.65 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h and then diluted with ether. Precipitated materials were discarded and aqueous sodium thiosulfate was added. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether and the combined organic layers washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated at reduced pressure. Purification by flash column chromatography resulted in 2-methoxyacetylthiane (0.39 g, 72%), ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 4.25 (2H, AB, J_{AB} 17 Hz), 3.60 (1H, t), 3.43 (3H, s), 2.64–2.71 (1H, m), 2.52–2.59 (1H, m), 1.90–2.05 (3H, m), 1.72–1.86 (2H, m), 1.47–1.59 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 205.2, 75.6, 59.3, 44.4, 27.5 (2C), 26.6, 23.2.

Methylmagnesium iodide addition to 2-methoxyacetylthiane: The reaction was carried out essentially as described above for 2-benzoylthiane resulting in a mixture of diastereomers in 20 : 80 ratio disfavoring the isomer involving chelation to the oxathiane ring: ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ [(3.45, 3.17)*, (3.35, 3.23), 2H, 2AB], 3.33 (3H, s), [2.96, 2.86* (1H, dd, J 11.6, 2.0 Hz)], 2.40–2.65 (2H, m), 1.16–2.20 (6H, m), [1.15, 1.10* (3H, s)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 77.4, 73.7, 73.5*, 59.2, 50.8, 49.4*, 29.7*, 29.4, 28.9, 27.8*, 27.2*, 27.0, 26.7*, 26.6, 21.7, 20.1* (*belongs to minor diastereomer).

Dimethylcopperlithium addition to 2-methoxyacetylthiane: The reaction was carried out as described above for 2-benzoylthiane but on half the scale, resulting in a mixture of diastereomeric carbinols in a 15 : 85 ratio favoring the same diastereomer as MeMgI: ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ [(3.46, 3.17)*, (3.36, 3.23), 2H, 2AB], 3.33 (3H, s), [2.96, 2.87* (1H, d)], 2.40–2.72 (2H, m), 1.78–2.20 (2H, m), 1.18–1.58 (4H, m), [1.15, 1.11* (3H, s)]; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 77.4, 73.7, 73.5*, 59.2, 50.9, 49.5*, 29.7*, 29.5, 29.0, 27.9*, 27.3*, 27.0, 26.6, 21.6, 20.1* (*belongs to minor diastereomer).

Methylthium-YbCl₃ addition to 2-methoxyacetylthiane: The reaction was effected as described for 2-benzoyloxane above, but on half the scale, to yield a mixture of diastereomeric carbinols in a 15 : 85 ratio, favoring the same isomer as Me_2CuLi , as shown by NMR spectra.

Addition of pentynyllithium to 2-methoxyacetylthiane: The reaction was carried out as described for 2-benzoylthiane above. NMR analysis of the crude product indicated very high diastereoselectivity (1 : 99): ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.49 (2H, AB, J_{AB} 9.6 Hz), 3.38 (3H, s), 3.02 (1H, dd), 2.84 (1H, br), 2.55–2.70 (2H, m), 2.16 (2H, t), 1.18–2.12 (8H, m), 0.94 (3H, t); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 86.5, 79.5, 76.8, 72.6, 59.5, 49.6, 29.1, 29.0, 26.8, 25.9, 21.8, 20.6, 13.3.

Addition of pentynyllithium-YbCl₃ to 2-methoxyacetylthiane: The reaction was carried out as described for 2-benzoylthiane above. The proton NMR of the crude sample indicated a diastereomer ratio of 2 : 98 favoring the same product as obtained in absence of YbCl_3 , as demonstrated by the identity of the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra.

Oxidation of products of addition of MeMgI and Me₂CuLi: Products of the two addition reactions were combined and purified by flash column chromatography to a 10 : 90 mixture of diastereomers. This material (90 mg, 0.47 mmol) was dissolved in 4 : 1 mixture of acetone : methanol (5 ml) and stirred with H_2O_2 (0.128 ml of 30% solution, 1.00 mmol), monoperoxyphthalic acid magnesium salt hexahydrate (495 mg, 1.00 mmol) and two drops of glacial acetic acid. The reaction was followed by TLC and was complete in 3.5 h. Concentration under reduced pressure followed by flash column chromatography silica gel equipped with a pad of K_2CO_3 yielded the expected sulfone (70 mg, 67%) with a 7 : 93 diastereomeric ratio. Single crystal X-ray analysis (Fig. 5) of the major diastereomer showed the configuration to be R^*,R^* : ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.65 (1H, br), 3.38 (2H, s), 3.34 (3H, s), 3.26 (1H, dd), 2.88–3.02 (2H, m), 1.84–2.13 (5H, m), 1.34–1.51 (1H, m), 1.34 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 78.0, 74.3, 66.2, 59.2, 54.3, 26.4, 24.6, 24.2, 23.0.

X-Ray crystallographic data: The crystallographic data for the compounds named and depicted as Ortep projections in Figs. 1–4 have been deposited in the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Base.

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